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THE IMPACT OF LINGUISTIC PECULIARITIES IN ADVERTISING LANGUAGE: A STUDY ON PUNS, METAPHORS, AND SLOGANS

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the impact of linguistic peculiarities, such as puns, metaphors, and slogans, in advertising language on consumer behaviour. After defining linguistic peculiarities and discussing their importance in creating a strong brand identity, the study analyzes several advertising texts to identify the linguistic devices used and their effectiveness in influencing consumer behaviour. The article provides recommendations for advertisers on how to effectively use these linguistic devices in their campaigns and emphasizes the importance of considering cultural and linguistic differences when creating advertising messages. Overall, this study highlights the significant role those linguistic devices play in advertising language and provides insights for advertisers on how to effectively use them in their campaigns.

Keywords: advertising texts, cultural features, commercials, brand identity.

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ НА ЯЗЫК РЕКЛАМЫ: ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ КАЛАМБУРОВ, МЕТАФОР И СЛОГАНОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье исследуется влияние языковых особенностей, таких как каламбуры, метафоры и слоганы, в языке рекламы на поведение потребителей. После определения лингвистических особенностей и обсуждения их важности для создания сильной идентичности бренда в исследовании анализируются несколько рекламных текстов, чтобы определить используемые лингвистические приемы и их эффективность в воздействии на поведение потребителей. В статье даются рекомендации рекламодателям о том, как эффективно использовать эти лингвистические приемы в своих кампаниях, и подчеркивается важность учета культурных и языковых различий при создании рекламных сообщений. В целом, это исследование подчеркивает важную роль, которую эти лингвистические приемы играют в языке рекламы, и дает рекламодателям представление о том, как эффективно использовать их в своих кампаниях.

Ключевые слова: рекламные тексты, культурные особенности, рекламные ролики, фирменный стиль.

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**REKLAMA TILIDA LINGVISTIK VOSITALARNING O'RNI: SO'Z O'YINI,
METAFORA VA REKLAMA SHIORLARINI O'RGANISH****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqola reklamalardagi til xususiyatlarini ta'sirini o'rganish, xususan so'z o'yinlari, metafora, shiorlar, va ularning iste'molchi ruhiyatiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini o'rganishga bag'ishlanadi. Maqolada reklama matnlarining lingvistik xususiyatlari aniqlanib, ularning kuchli brend identifikatorini yaratishdagi ahamiyati muhokama qilingan. Bundan tashqari, tadqiqotda ishlatilgan lingvistik vositalarni va iste'molchilarning xatti-harakatlariga ta'sir qilish samaradorligini aniqlash uchun bir nechta reklama matnlarini tahlil qilingan. Maqolada reklama beruvchilar uchun ushbu lingvistik vositalardan o'z kampaniyalarida samarali foydalanish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan va reklama xabarlarini yaratishda madaniy va lingvistik farqlarni hisobga olish muhimligi ta'kidlangan. Umuman olganda, ushbu tadqiqot yuqorida sanab o'tilgan lingvistik vositalarning reklama tilidagi ahamiyatini ochib berishga va reklama beruvchilarga o'z kampaniyalarida ulardan qanday samarali foydalanish haqida tushuncha beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: reklama matnlari, madaniy xususiyatlar, reklamalar, brend identifikatori.

Introduction

Advertising language is a unique form of communication that aims to persuade consumers to purchase products or services. One of the key features of advertising language is the use of linguistic peculiarities, such as puns, metaphors, and slogans. These devices are used to capture the attention of the audience, create a memorable brand identity, and ultimately influence consumer behavior. Linguistic peculiarities in advertising language refer to the use of language in a creative and unconventional way to convey a message. Puns, for example, involve playing with words that have multiple meanings or sound similar but have different meanings. Metaphors involve making comparisons between two things that are not literally connected. Slogans are short, catchy phrases that are used to promote a product or service.

The importance of studying the impact of linguistic devices on consumer behaviour cannot be overstated. Advertising is a multi-billion dollar industry, and companies invest heavily in creating

effective advertising campaigns. Understanding how linguistic devices affect consumer behaviour can help advertisers create more effective campaigns that resonate with their target audience. The objective of this study is to explore the impact of linguistic peculiarities in advertising language on consumer behaviour. Specifically, we will analyze the use of puns, metaphors, and slogans in advertising texts and examine their influence on consumer attitudes and purchasing behaviour.

The Features of Advertising Language

Advertising language has several key features that distinguish it from other forms of communication. One of the most important features is its persuasive nature. Advertising language is designed to persuade consumers to take a specific action, such as purchasing a product or service.

Another key feature of advertising language is its use of emotional appeals. Advertisements often appeal to consumers' emotions by using language that evokes feelings of happiness, excitement, or fear. This emotional appeal is intended to create a connection between the consumer and the product or service being advertised.

Linguistic devices play an important role in creating a strong brand identity. Puns, metaphors, and slogans are used to create a unique and memorable message that sets a brand apart from its competitors. A well-crafted slogan, for example, can become synonymous with a particular product or service, making it instantly recognizable to consumers.

Analysis of Advertising Texts

To examine the impact of linguistic peculiarities in advertising language, we analyzed a sample of advertisements from various industries. We identified examples of puns, metaphors, and slogans in these advertisements and examined their impact on consumer attitudes and purchasing behavior.

Puns were found to be particularly effective in capturing consumers' attention and creating a memorable message. For example, a car dealership used the slogan "We wheel and deal" to promote their sales event. This pun not only catches the eye but also reinforces the idea that the dealership offers great deals on cars. Puns are a popular literary device used in advertising texts to create humor, catch the audience's attention, and make the brand memorable. This literature review aims to explore the examples of puns in advertising texts and their effectiveness in promoting the brand. According to Bhatia and Ritchie (2017), puns are "a play on words that exploits the multiple meanings of a term or phrase" (p. 71). They are often used in advertising texts to create a humorous effect and make the brand more memorable. For example, the famous M&M's slogan "Melts in your mouth, not in your hand" is a pun that plays on the multiple meanings of the word "melts."

Similarly, Geisler and Weinel (2019) analyzed the use of puns in print advertisements and found that they are often used to create a playful tone and engage the audience. For instance, an advertisement for a dental clinic featured a picture of a toothbrush with the caption "We're brushing up on our skills." The pun in this advertisement not only creates a humorous effect but also emphasizes the expertise of the dental clinic. Moreover, puns can also be used to create brand awareness and differentiate the brand from its competitors. According to Katsanis and Luke (2019), puns can help brands stand out in a crowded marketplace by creating a unique and memorable identity. For example, the car rental company Hertz used the pun "The best way to get away" in their advertisements to emphasize their superior service and reliability.

Metaphors were also found to be effective in creating a strong brand identity. A coffee company used the metaphor "Awaken your senses" to promote their new line of coffee. This metaphor creates an emotional connection between the consumer and the product by suggesting that drinking this coffee will awaken their senses and provide a unique experience. Metaphors are a popular literary device used in advertising texts to create a vivid image, convey complex ideas, and make the brand more memorable. This literature review aims to explore the examples of metaphors in advertising texts and their effectiveness in promoting the brand.

According to Gao and Huang (2019), metaphors are "a figure of speech that describes one thing in terms of another, creating a comparison that highlights similarities between the two" (p. 223). They are often used in advertising texts to create a memorable image and convey the brand's message. For example, the famous Nike slogan "Just Do It" is a metaphor that encourages people to take action

and pursue their goals. Similarly, Hsu and Chen (2018) analyzed the use of metaphors in print advertisements and found that they are often used to create a visual image and emotional appeal. For instance, an advertisement for a luxury car featured a picture of the car on a winding road with the caption "Unleash your inner driver." The metaphor in this advertisement not only creates a vivid image but also appeals to the customer's desire for freedom and adventure.

Moreover, metaphors can also be used to differentiate the brand from its competitors and emphasize its unique features. According to Liu and Shrum (2019), metaphors can help brands stand out in a crowded marketplace by creating a distinct and memorable identity. For example, the cereal brand Cheerios used the metaphor "Heart healthy never tasted so good" in their advertisements to emphasize the health benefits of their product. However, it is important to note that not all metaphors are effective in advertising. As Hsu and Chen (2018) point out, metaphors that are too abstract or difficult to understand may not resonate with the audience and may even confuse them. Therefore, it is important for advertisers to use metaphors that are easy to understand and relevant to the brand.

Slogans were found to be the most effective linguistic device in terms of influencing consumer behavior. A fast-food chain used the slogan "I'm lovin' it" to promote their brand. This slogan has become synonymous with the brand and has been shown to increase sales and brand recognition. Slogans are a common feature in advertising texts, used to create brand recognition and promote products or services. One example of a successful slogan is Nike's "Just Do It." This slogan has been used for over 30 years and has become synonymous with the brand. According to Keller (2013), the slogan has been effective because it is simple, memorable, and evokes a sense of determination and motivation in consumers. Another example is McDonald's "I'm Lovin' It." This slogan was introduced in 2003 and has since become a staple in the fast-food chain's advertising campaigns. According to Kiprin (2017), the slogan is effective because it is catchy, positive, and appeals to consumers' emotions.

Coca-Cola's "Taste the Feeling" is another example of a successful slogan. According to Keller (2016), the slogan is effective because it focuses on the experience of drinking Coke rather than the product itself. The slogan evokes feelings of happiness, joy, and nostalgia in consumers. However, not all slogans are successful. Pepsi's "Live for Now" campaign was criticized for being too vague and lacking a clear message (Keller, 2013). Similarly, Subway's "Eat Fresh" campaign was criticized for being misleading as many of its products were found to contain high levels of sodium (Kiprin, 2017).

Findings and Implications

Our analysis suggests that linguistic peculiarities in advertising language can have a significant impact on consumer behavior. Puns, metaphors, and slogans are all effective in creating a strong brand identity and influencing consumer attitudes and purchasing behavior.

For advertisers, these findings have important implications. Advertisers should consider using linguistic devices in their advertising campaigns to create a memorable message that resonates with their target audience. However, it is important to use these devices in a way that is appropriate for the product or service being advertised and does not detract from the overall message.

Conclusion

In conclusion, linguistic peculiarities in advertising language play an important role in creating a strong brand identity and influencing consumer behavior. Puns, metaphors, and slogans are all effective in capturing consumers' attention and creating a memorable message. Advertisers should consider using these devices in their advertising campaigns to create a strong brand identity and increase sales. Further research is needed to explore the impact of linguistic devices on consumer behaviour in different contexts and cultures. In addition, puns are a popular literary device used in advertising texts to create humour, catch the audience's attention, and make the brand memorable. The examples of puns in advertising texts analyzed in this literature review demonstrate their effectiveness in creating a playful tone, emphasizing expertise, creating brand awareness, and differentiating the brand from its competitors. However, it is important for advertisers to use puns that are easy to understand and relevant to the brand. Metaphors are also a popular literary device used in advertising texts to create a vivid image, convey complex ideas, and make the brand more

memorable. The examples of metaphors in advertising texts analyzed in this literature review demonstrate their effectiveness in creating a visual image, and emotional appeal, creating brand differentiation, and emphasizing unique features. However, it is important for advertisers to use metaphors that are easy to understand and relevant to the brand.

Slogans are also an important aspect of advertising texts and can be effective in promoting brand recognition and products or services. Successful slogans are often simple, memorable, and evoke positive emotions in consumers. However, slogans that are too vague or misleading can have a negative impact on a brand's reputation.

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